

LPJ-GUESS European applications update, svn revision 12626

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1. Summary

This report describes a reparameterisation of the europe.ins file for LPJ-GUESS in order to bring the settings up to date with the latest observations and to improve the performance of the model with respect to simulating stand structure in Europe. A new branch, european_applications, has been created in the LPJ-GUESS community subversion repository and instruction file parameters for which direct observations are available have been updated. A range of further modifications and fixes have also been implemented. The new branch has then been benchmarked against NFI observations and satellite GPP. This benchmarking identified a low bias in woody growth rate, which was causing a general underestimation of biomass. A calibration process was carried out to correct this, based on parameters for which only weak constraints are available. The resulting model version performs notably better against benchmarks, including those which were not used in the calibration process. This version of european_applications (svn r12626) forms a basis for future work in on-going European forestry projects. The updated instruction files are found within the code in /data/ins.

2. Code base and updates

This document uses the european_applications branch in the LPJ-GUESS community subversion repository. Revision r12626 is the recommended revision on which to base new simulations. This branch was created from trunk r11300 (currently synced to trunk r11481). Key updates compared to the trunk version are:

- Updated allocation approach (ported from branch new_allocation)
- Establishment fix to avoid unintended behaviour in monocultures where, if only one woody PFT was specified, establishment was increased by a factor of 3 (r11381).
- Maximum crown area (crownarea_max) limit removed.
- Bole height set to 0.5 throughout. This changes competition in mixed stands, but has no effect in even-aged monocultures.
- No allocation of NPP to reproduction until a tree reaches the number of years defined by the PFT parameter repage (Table A1).
- New europe.ins file with parameter updates as described below.

Minor technical updates or those incident to this document include:

- Netcdf inputs (branch tech_cfx)
- New outputs to facilitate comparison with forest inventory data
- Merging with storm module and windload input (r11641).

PFT parameters for which direct and good quality observations are available were updated directly with those parameters, taking the approach that LPJ-GUESS should be as closely tied to reality as possible. Updated parameters are:

- SLA (TRY request 6033),
- k_latosa (Liu et al. in prep dataset from the TreeMort project; [Peguero-Pina et al., 2011](#) for Abies Alba)
- Wood density (Global wood density database; [Zanne et al., 2009](#))
- Allometric parameters for k_allom{1,2,3} and k_rp, calculated based on the TALLO database.

The full list of updated parameters is given in Table A1.

3. Simulation setup

Climate data: CRUNCEP

Resolution: 0.5° x 0.5°

Domain: Spain, France, Switzerland, Belgium, Netherlands, Germany, Czech Republic, Poland, Sweden, Finland, Norway.

Forest initialisation: Only forest was simulated. Stand age was initialised based on [Pucher et al. \(2022\)](#), using the landcover and stand type input files to reconstruct the stand age distribution observed in 2010. Forest composition was initialised based on NFI observations in each grid cell. 27 stand types were specified including both monospecific and mixed species stands. The stand type definitions used the European PFTs corresponding to the observations when possible. Species observed in the data but included in the European PFTs were categorised based on the species type (conifer/broadleaved) and shade tolerance (tolerant/intermediate/intolerant) and European PFTs with corresponding characteristics were used in the stand type definition.

Management: Clearcut harvest is accounted for based on the stand-age initialisation, but the past thinning regime is unknown. For this reason two simulations were conducted, both without thinning and with idealised thinning based on the Reineke rule. It is expected that the true regime lies somewhere between these two extremes.

4. Evaluation data

Information from national forest inventory (NFI) plots (or other forest inventory data in the case of the Czech Republic) was summarised on a 0.5° grid. Only trees with DBH ≥ 10 cm (except a minimum DBH of 12 cm for Switzerland) were considered from any of the data sets, and trees were weighted by their inverse sampling probability on a hectare to account for different plot sizes and designs between the countries.

The evaluation data contained the following variables (calculated from the NFI data if not stated otherwise):

- Average plot quadratic mean diameter (mm)
- Woody biomass (Mg ha^{-1})
- Average plot stem density (stems ha^{-1})

- Woody biomass growth ($\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{y}^{-1}$), calculated as the biomass in census 2 minus the biomass in census 1, plus the biomass lost to mortality during the census period.
- Conifer share of the woody biomass (note that this is essentially a cross-check on the competition, since the basic composition of what is allowed to established is prescribed based on the same observations)
- Stem density per tree size class (classes in 5 cm diameter intervals: 10-15 cm, 15-20 cm, etc.)
- Woody biomass per tree size class (classes in 5 cm diameter intervals)

In addition we compared to gross primary productivity (GPP) ($\text{kg C m}^{-2} \text{y}^{-1}$) data. Modelled Annual GPP from [Tagesson et al. \(2020\)](#) was processed at 0.05° and aggregated to 0.5° taking the grid-cell mean value. 0.05° forest pixels were isolated before aggregation using the Corine Land Cover dataset (CLC) (100m) from [Copernicus Land Monitoring Service 2018, European Environment Agency \(EEA\)](#). Using CLC, a threshold was set to each GPP grid cell, removing all cells with less than 80% forest cover.

5. Calibration process

Based upon an initial assessment of LPJ-GUESS performance against the evaluation data, it was identified that there was a general low bias in biomass and in woody growth rate. Given that the simulations were initialised based on observed stand age, woody growth rate was identified as the core variable in need of improvement. It was also identified that the carbon use efficiency was generally very low compared to independent estimates ([Zhang et al., 2014](#)). We carried out an assessment of parameters for calibration based on expert judgement, identifying those which are known to have a substantial impact on woody growth rate, but for which strong observational constraints are not available. Based on this, the autotrophic respiration coefficient (respcoeff) and sapwood turnover rate (turnover_sap) were identified for calibration. Sapwood turnover rate is generally set at the shade-tolerance class level, so this split was maintained, giving a total of 3 parameters to calibrate. Possible values for sapwood turnover for each species were constrained so as to ensure that shade-tolerance classes were respected. Respcoeff is included in the model to account for the differences in baseline respiration rates as a result of climate adaptation, but is set to 1.0 across the whole of Europe. Given that climate is the primary driver ([Aitkin et al., 2015](#)), we split the species/PFTs into two groups based on whether they were predominantly boreal or north-central temperate zone (cold) or southern temperate zone (warm), we also split it into needleleaved and broadleaved following [Aitkin et al., \(2015\)](#). This gave a total of 7 parameters for the calibration process.

A calibration transect of 59 grid cells was selected from the simulation setup described in section 3 above, randomly selecting one for each degree of latitude (Figure 1). In order to avoid inadvertently calibrating LPJ-GUESS against extreme values, only grid cells with growth rate values between the 25th and 75th quartiles were available for selection. We performed 6760 simulations across the gradient with the permutations (steps of 4 between the values given in Table 1) for the 7 selected parameters that met the following requirements: (a) turnover_sap for the more tolerant should always be lower or equal to that of a less shade tolerant class; (b) respcoeff should be higher for the warm class within its leaf physiognomic class. This latter response was based on assessments showing carbon use efficiency to tend

towards higher values at cooler locations ([Zhang et al., 2014](#)). We selected the top performing simulations by maximising the ratio of the correlation coefficient and RMSE calculated in comparison with the observations of growth rate. Woody growth rate is the only variable included in the objective function because it is the only part of the inventory observations whose values are not heavily determined by assumptions regarding the thinning regime. The *optimal* simulation setup is based on the mean of the top 10 simulations based on this metric.

Figure 1. Locations of grid cells used for the calibration. Colours indicate the GPP ($\text{kg C m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) in a simulation with the *euro_initial* version (see Table 2).

Table 1. Parameter ranges used in the calibration.

Parameter	Minimum	Maximum
respcoeff, needle leaved, cold	0.25	0.75
respcoeff, needle leaved, warm	0.25	0.75
respcoeff, broadleaved, cold	0.5	1.0
respcoeff, broadleaved, warm	0.5	1.0
turnover_sap, shade tolerant	0.025	0.075
turnover_sap, int. shade tolerant	0.05	0.1
turnover_sap, shade intolerant	0.075	0.125

6. Results and discussion

Table 2 describes the European simulations that were conducted and shows the results for the calibrated parameters. Only results for the *trunk* and *optimal* (euro_opt) simulations are displayed in the following section.

Table 2. European simulations conducted and results of the calibration.

Simulation name	respcoeff				turnover_sap			Parameters as listed in Table A1
	Broad Cold	Broad Warm	Needle Cold	Needle Warm	shade intolerant	intermediate shade tolerant	shade tolerant	
trunk	1	1	1	1	0.05	0.075	0.1	trunk
euro_initial	1	1	1	1	0.05	0.075	0.1	trunk
euro_traits_only	1	1	1	1	0.05	0.075	0.1	updated
euro_opt	0.67	0.97	0.58	0.62	0.072	0.1	0.117	updated
euro_opt1	0.67	0.83	0.58	0.58	0.075	0.1	0.108	updated
euro_opt2	0.67	0.83	0.58	0.75	0.075	0.1	0.108	updated
euro_opt3	0.67	1	0.58	0.42	0.075	0.1	0.108	updated
euro_opt4	0.67	1	0.58	0.42	0.075	0.1	0.125	updated
euro_opt5	0.67	1	0.58	0.58	0.058	0.1	0.125	updated
euro_opt6	0.67	1	0.58	0.58	0.075	0.1	0.108	updated
euro_opt7	0.67	1	0.58	0.58	0.075	0.1	0.125	updated
euro_opt8	0.67	1	0.58	0.75	0.058	0.1	0.125	updated
euro_opt9	0.67	1	0.58	0.75	0.075	0.1	0.108	updated
euro_opt10	0.67	1	0.58	0.75	0.075	0.1	0.125	updated

euro_initial: code base update without updated PFT parameters

euro_traits_only: code base update with updated PFT parameters

euro_opt: fully calibrated *optimal* setup, based on the mean of the five best parameter sets

euro_opt1,2,3,4,5: calibration results for each of the five best parameter sets.

Overall, the optimal simulations are closer to mean values across the domain for all metrics, but with improvements most marked for growth rate and biomass (Table 3). The *trunk* version of LPJ-GUESS shows a generalised and substantial underestimation of woody growth rate in all regions except Sweden and Finland (Figure 2). In the *optimal* version this underestimation has been largely resolved. There is little difference between simulations with thinning and those without. Whilst woody growth has been increased, the GPP has generally decreased in the *optimal* simulation, compared to the *trunk*, resulting in a better agreement with the reference dataset. Generally, GPP was substantially higher in LPJ-GUESS than the reference dataset in the *trunk* version (Figure 3). Whilst the reference dataset is also a model product, the increased agreement is encouraging, particularly as it results from a reduction in GPP that

has occurred from a calibration process that boosted woody growth. This reduction in GPP is associated with a modest reduction in leaf area index (not shown), which is a plausible outcome of the changes in respcoeff and turnover_{sap}.

Table 3. Summary statistics calculated as the unweighted mean of all grid cells across the whole simulation domain.

		optimal	trunk	Observations
Woody growth	Kg C m ⁻² yr ⁻¹	0.220	0.175	0.218
GPP	Kg C m ⁻² yr ⁻¹	1.25	1.33	1.05
AGB	Kg C m ⁻²	6.57	5.15	7.16
Stem density	Indiv ha ⁻¹	412	398	527
Quadratic DBH	cm	25.2	26.2	23.2

The increase in woody growth rate has resulted in a higher biomass in the *optimal* simulation, compared to *trunk*. In the *trunk*, biomass was routinely underestimated even without thinning in all regions apart from the Nordics. Biomass in the *optimal* simulation is generally consistent with, or lower than, the observations when Reineke thinning is applied, or overestimated compared to the observations when no thinning is applied (Figure 4). This is consistent with the expectation that these two settings represent the two extremes of possibility. Sweden and Finland present an exception, where there is a slight tendency to overestimate biomass in the *optimal* simulation with thinning. However, this tendency is slight and intensive and highly-regulated management in these countries means that Reineke thinning may not be a major divergence from reality – although this remains conjecture. Southern/central Germany is also an exception, where biomass is always underestimated, although the underestimation is reduced in the *optimal* simulations compared to *trunk*. This is consistent with a remaining low-growth bias in this region (Fig. 2). It may be that a single parameter set for each of *picea abies* and *pinus sylvestris*, two of the most common species across Germany and the Nordics, is not appropriate across their entire extensive range, leading to these biases. However, this would require further model development for these specific species.

Generally, LPJ-GUESS simulations with and without thinning straddle the observations for stand density (Figure 5). Whilst this is consistent with the expectation that the real thinning regime lies between these two extremes, considering these results in the context of Figures 2-4 implies that some biases remain. For instance, if the interpretation above that Reineke thinning is a reasonable first order approximation for Sweden and Finland is correct, then LPJ-GUESS would tend to substantially underestimate stand density (and modestly overestimate diameter; Fig. 6) in these regions. Quadratic mean diameter presents a much more mixed picture, with areas of substantial under and overestimation by region which broadly, but not entirely, correspond with the biomass deviations. In arid parts of Spain, diameter is generally underestimated regardless of thinning regime, whilst density is typically overestimated.

Figure 7 breaks down the overall simulation AGB by the *optimal* simulation according to the contributions of the individual PFTs. Most species can be found growing across their expected ranges. *Ulmus glabra* stands out as having a particularly high biomass, which is enhanced relative to the *trunk* simulation (Figure 8). *Fagus sylvatica* has a slightly lower biomass compared to the trunk simulation. The broad range of *Larix decidua* is reflective of decisions in the input dataset which caused it to be planted outside of its range and is not reflective of the bioclimatic limits in LPJ-GUESS.

Given the uncertainty in the past and present harvest rates, the only comparisons where we could reasonably expect a model which is a perfect representation of reality to correspond closely to the observations are those against woody growth rate and GPP. However, that the structural variables do not always present biases against observations that appear consistent with each other highlights some regions where further investigation is necessary. It may be that some of these apparent biases result from limitations in the stand age data used to initialise the simulations. However, it could also be that a more substantial revision of how canopy competition and structure are represented may be required to resolve these limitations. Such a development is currently in testing but is not anticipated to be deployed rapidly in the european_applications or trunk versions of LPJ-GUESS.

Figure 2. Anomaly of woody growth rate (model - observations) for the trunk (top row) and optimal (bottom row) simulations, without thinning (left column) and with Reineke thinning (right column). Insets show heat plots of the model against observations (warmer colours signify more grid cells), with the 1:1 line in red.

Figure 3. As for Figure 2 except for gross primary productivity. Fewer pixels are included in the comparison because GPP data was only included for pixels dominated by forest.

Figure 4. As for Figure 2 except for above-ground biomass.

Figure 5. As for Figure 2 except for stem density.

Figure 6. As for Figure 2 except for quadratic mean DBH.

Figure 7. Total above-ground biomass carbon simulated per species for the optimal simulation with thinning. Values are weighted contributed of each PFT to the grid cell total.

Figure 8. As for Figure 7 except showing the difference between optimal and trunk simulations. Blue values correspond to higher AGB in the optimal simulation.

7. Conclusion

Based on the metrics assessed here, the optimal setup for LPJ-GUESS in Europe appears to offer notable performance improvements compared to the current trunk. It is also based on PFT/species parameters that are well-grounded in the latest observations where possible. It is therefore recommended to base future simulations for the European continent on this version.

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Appendix

Table A1. Updated instruction file parameter values based on observations. Units as per instruction file defaults.

species /PFT	repr age	sla	bole_ratio	k_allo m2	k_allo m3	k_rp	wood dens	cton_root	k_allo m1	fnstor age	longevity	k_lato sa
Abi_alb	60	14.85	0.5	54.2	0.796	1.109	252.5	29	61	0.05	350	4000
BES	20	10	0	5	0.67	1.6	250	29	20	0.3	50	500
Bet_pen	20	32.6	0.5	58.2	0.675	1.43	285	29	193.4	0.15	200	5000
Bet_pub	20	48.26	0.5	21.1	0.289	1.135	267.5	29	88.9	0.15	200	5000
Car_bet	30	39.9	0.5	34.3	0.476	1.277	340	29	213.8	0.15	350	5000
Cor_ave	30	34.2	0.5	29.3	0.461	1	292.5	29	109.1	0.15	100	4000
Fag_syl	50	57	0.5	34.2	0.445	1.242	337.5	29	157.4	0.15	500	5000
Fra_exc	30	29.4	0.5	58.7	0.684	1.358	332.5	29	104.8	0.15	350	5000
Jun_oxy	20	13	0.5	29.3	0.461	1.358	287.5	29	104.8	0.05	200	1500
Lar_dec	30	13	0.5	51	0.5	1.109	262.5	29	61	0.05	500	5000
MRS	20	10	0	5	0.67	1.6	250	29	100	0.3	100	1500
Pic_abi	50	12.6	0.5	61.2	0.818	1.103	225	29	59.4	0.05	500	4000
Pin_syl	30	10.9	0.5	30.7	0.582	1.552	282.5	29	118.6	0.05	350	3000
Pin_hal	20	11.2	0.5	20.6	0.65	1.407	307.5	29	130.8	0.05	350	3000
Pop_tre	20	29.1	0.5	49.2	0.623	1.235	238.8	29	106.6	0.15	160	5000
Que_coc	30	25.5	0	36.1	0.548	1.054	257.5	29	191.8	0.3	350	2500

Que_ile	30	13.3	0.5	9.6	0.333	1.617	420	29	196	0.05	350	3000
Que_pub	30	24.9	0.5	15.4	0.387	1.48	377.5	29	144.3	0.15	500	5000
Que_rob	60	22.8	0.5	24.6	0.503	1.466	307.5	29	176.4	0.15	500	5000
Til_cor	30	45.4	0.5	44.2	0.575	1	227.5	29	30.3	0.15	350	5000
Ulm_gla	25	31.3	0.5	41.1	0.643	1.253	312.5	29	207.6	0.15	350	5000

Table A2. Assignment of species/PFTs to shade-tolerance and region groups for calibration.

species/ PFT	Broad Cold	Broad Warm	Needle Cold	Needle Warm	Shade tolerant	Intermediate shade tolerant	Shade intolerant
Abi_alb			1		1		
BES			1				1
Bet_pen	1						1
Bet_pub	1						1
Car_bet	1					1	
Cor_ave	1					1	
Fag_syl	1				1		
Fra_exc		1				1	
Jun_oxy				1			1
Lar_dec			1			1	
MRS		1					1

Pic_abi			1			1		
Pic_sit			1				1	
Pin_syl			1				1	
Pin_hal					1			1
Pop_tre		1						1
Que_coc		1					1	
Que_ile		1					1	
Que_pub		1					1	
Que_rob	1						1	
Til_cor	1						1	
Ulm_gla	1						1	